

NATIONAL ACADEMY OF SCIENCES OF UKRAINE
MINISTRY OF EDUCATION AND SCIENCE OF UKRAINE
NATIONAL AVIATION UNIVERSITY

Kyiv

The Seventh World Congress "AVIATION IN THE XXI-st CENTURY"
Safety in Aviation and Space Technologies

September 19-21, 2016

The Development of Ideas about Human Factor

Oleksandr Petrenko

Conference Paper

Presented at the Seventh World Congress "Aviation in the XXI-st Century – Safety in aviation and space technology", National Aviation University, Kyiv, Ukraine, September 19-21, 2016

Full citation:

Petrenko, O.V. (2016). *The Development of Ideas about Human Factor*. In: *Proceeding of The Seventh World Congress "Aviation in the XXI-st Century – Safety in aviation and space technology"*, pp. 3.5.16–3.5.20. National Aviation University, Kyiv.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15913553>

<https://er.nau.edu.ua/handle/NAU/62785>

The Development of Ideas about Human Factor

This paper explores the interconnections between, on the one hand, the objective requirements placed on humans within socio-technical systems and the design philosophy held by system developers, and, on the other hand, the actual performance characteristics and professional worldviews of personnel shaped by specific organizational cultures. These relationships are examined through the lens of organizational culture as a core component of the human factor framework. The paper introduces a model of dangerous inconsistencies in socio-technical systems, which highlights critical misalignments that may compromise system reliability.

As practice shows, automation opens up new opportunities for human activity but also introduces additional challenges. Clearly, approaching innovation from the perspective of the human factor—that is, considering the full range of consequences arising from human interaction with information, tools, tasks, and rules of operation, as well as with the physical and social environment—can substantially enhance both the improvement of existing and the development of new socio-technical systems.

The human factor is distinguished by the complexity of its internal structure and the interdependence of its components. This complexity makes it difficult to evaluate and adjust the consequences of ongoing technological and equipment development in terms of the role and capabilities of human operators.

The evolution of human factor models reflects a consistent effort to capture its essential aspects in a comprehensive way (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Variants of human factors models: a) the SHEL model (E. Edwards, 1972); b) the SHELL model (F.H. Hawkins, 1987); c) the variant of presentation of the SCHELL human factors model [7] (A. Keightley, 2004).

Thus, the development of E. Edwards's concept (Fig. 1a) was followed by an improved model proposed by F.H. Hawkins (Fig. 1b), which introduced an additional element: "Liveware–Liveware" interactions. In Hawkins's version, the

outer Liveware element (L) represents group-related factors such as teamwork, communication, leadership, and social norms. Meanwhile, the central Liveware element reflects various individual human characteristics, including knowledge, attitudes, cultural background, stress manifestations, and more [2].

A key question arises: how important is the interconnection between the Software (S) and Hardware (H) components for a more nuanced analysis? The original SHELL model considers this relationship, while the SHELL model does not explicitly account for it.

An argument in favor of highlighting this connection is that both equipment and operational rules are developed by people, and are therefore shaped by their ideas about human characteristics and approaches to optimizing human performance. These ideas may vary significantly from one individual or group to another.

A human being, as a personality, possesses an internal world comprised of aspirations, emotions, ethical orientations, and subjective meaning. This becomes especially evident in professional activity. Whereas physiological and psychophysiological characteristics largely determine a human operator's physical limitations and capabilities, psychological and socio-cultural factors exert a more complex influence. They shape what an individual brings to a work situation—including values, behavioral tendencies, interpersonal styles, communication skills, and both life and professional experience—formed through personal development over time.

Cultural (and socio-cultural) dimensions of the human factors problem have long attracted attention [3, 4], including in the context of improving Crew Resource Management (CRM) programs [5]. The socio-cultural dimension is explicitly represented in the SCHELL model (Fig. 1c), where the C component refers to "organizational and national cultures that influence interaction" [6, 7, 8].

We have analyzed the complex and often contradictory manifestations of the socio-cultural factor in the post-Soviet context, particularly in relation to regulating joint activity within flight crews and in the practice of CRM-based training [10, 11]. Our findings indicate the presence of phenomena that may directly compromise flight safety—especially in situations where divergent professional worldviews, traditions, and individual experience collide.

An analysis of CRM training programs common in the post-Soviet space shows that some of them directly contradict the core principles of modern CRM philosophy, yet remain consistent with inherited corporate cultures and prevailing professional belief systems [10]. During the transitional period following the societal transformation, a new layer of problems emerged. These were largely rooted in the introduction of interaction norms and rules—originally developed within different cultural frameworks—into the professional environment of the post-Soviet aviation sector.

The human factors model can be interpreted as a kind of *risk map* that helps identify hazardous areas of inconsistency within a socio-technical system. We observe that the model has been evolving by incorporating an increasing number of components. This evolution inevitably leads to greater complexity, yet certain phenomena associated with the human factor clearly require the introduction of additional conceptual constructs.

One possible way forward is to supplement the core model with other compatible frameworks designed to address aspects not explicitly represented in the main structure. Our next steps are directed toward this goal.

In domains involving the operation of complex technical systems, an important component of the human factor is what we refer to as *operating philosophy*. This concept encompasses the core ideas and requirements related to the structure and organization of human activity within socio-technical systems, as well as the strategies for ensuring both human reliability and overall system performance. One of its key functions is to align design solutions with specified operational procedures. More fundamentally, however, the operating philosophy serves as a conceptual integrator that ensures internal consistency across all components of the human factor.

The content of the operating philosophy is typically defined by the system's manufacturer and should be based on accumulated operational experience. A mismatch between the prescribed operating philosophy and the socio-cultural characteristics of the operating organization can pose a significant risk (see Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Field of operating philosophy manifestations

The operating philosophy must be internally consistent with both the corporate culture and the space of individual worldviews among personnel (see Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Acceptable interrelations spaces of operating and regulatory philosophy, corporate culture and individual weltanschauung

In our view, the operating philosophy is based on a dual understanding: first, of the opportunities and strengths of human capabilities, and second, of the vulnerabilities and limitations that may arise in specific operational contexts. It

should provide a conceptual framework for identifying situations and risks that can be addressed through human potential, as well as those that stem from intrinsic human constraints. Importantly, this perspective applies equally to individual and team-level activity (see Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Genesis of operating philosophy

In addition to the problem of maintaining a coherent professional culture within global aviation, there is also the challenge of ensuring conceptual alignment between the worldview of aviation system designers and that of operational personnel (see Fig. 5). The operating philosophy may become distorted during the implementation of design intent, due to various factors that emerge throughout the system's life cycle.

Fig. 5. Coherence of designers' and operators' worldviews as an aspect of the human factor

A professional worldview is shaped by the nature of the tasks performed, which differ fundamentally between aircraft designers and pilots. In the context of automation, the designer's perspective increasingly permeates the operator's workspace. It can be argued that developers of automated systems are virtually "present" in the cockpit—acting as invisible members of the flight crew [9]. In this sense, the divergence in worldviews between developers and operators can resemble the kinds of misunderstandings that arise within real-world teams.

Based on the above, we propose incorporating *operating philosophy* and *human-related requirements* into the domain of human factors analysis—specifically in relation to the actual cultural characteristics of professional teams and the real-world performance of personnel, which reflects their lived experience, capabilities, and individual worldviews (see Fig. 6) [12].

Fig. 6. The Model of Dangerous Inconsistencies in Socio-Technical System (Petrenko, 2015)

This model is conceptually aligned with the SCHELL framework and directs attention to the *zone of tension between what is objectively required and what is actually available*. It identifies four key areas for analysis (highlighted in red), namely:

- the degree of alignment between the cultural characteristics of a local professional group and:
 - a) the operating philosophy as envisioned by the system's designers;
 - b) the objective requirements for human performance in that professional domain;
- the degree of alignment between actual human performance characteristics and:
 - a) the objective requirements for human performance;
 - b) the operating philosophy as envisioned by the system's designers.

The proposed model of dangerous inconsistencies in socio-technical systems provides a structured means of integrating cultural context, operating philosophy,

and real human capabilities into human factors analysis. It enables the systematic identification of critical gaps between design expectations and actual performance conditions. These inconsistencies, while often latent, can present real risks to system safety and reliability. Expanding human factors frameworks in this direction appears both necessary and timely.

References

1. Edwards, E. Man and Machine: Systems for Safety // Proceedings of British Airline Pilots Association Technical Symposium. – London, 1972. – P. 21-36.
2. Hawkins F.H. Human factors in flight (2nd Ed.). – “Ashgate” (Aldershot, UK), 1987. – 384 p.
3. Hackman J.R. New Directions in Crew-Oriented Flight Training // ICAO Circular 229-AN/137. Human Factors Digest No: 4. Proceeding of the ICAO Human Factors Seminar. – Leningrad, 1990.
4. Hofstede G.H. Cultures and Organizations: Software of the Mind. – New York: McGraw-Hill, 1991. – 279 p.
5. Johnston N. CRM: Cross-cultural perspectives // Cockpit Resource Management / Ed. by Earl L. Wiener, Barbara G. Kanki, Robert L. Helmreich; with a foreword by John K. Lauber. – London, Academic Press, 1993. – P. 367-395.
6. SMS for Aviation – a Practical Guide. Civil Aviation Safety Authority, Australian Government. From: <https://www.casa.gov.au/sites/g/files/net351/f/assets/main/sms/download/2012-sms-book6-human-factors.pdf>
7. <http://captainpeterdann.com/2014/12/30/human-factors-what-are-they-and-why-are-they-important/>
8. Human Factors in Aviation: How Hogan Can Help. – Australia: Peter Berry Consultancy Pty Ltd, 2011. From: http://www.peterberry.com.au/files/white_papers/pbc_white_paper_-_using_the_hpi_and_hds_to_assess_human_factors_in_aviation
9. Petrenko O. Man-machine symbiosis in aviation: new risks and capabilities in view of information technology expansion / Oleksandr Petrenko // Proceedings of the 17-th International Symposium on Aviation Psychology. – Dayton, Ohio, USA: Right State University, 2013. – P. 116-121.
10. Петренко О.В. Психологічні аспекти управління ресурсами льотного екіпажу / Олександр Петренко // Актуальні проблеми психології: збірник наукових праць. – К.: 2010. – Т. X. – Вип. 17. – С. 346-355.
11. Петренко О.В. Соціокультурні регулятори ефективності льотного екіпажу // Матеріали IV науково-практичної конференції «Актуальні проблеми психології діяльності в особливих умовах» – Київ: НАУ, 2009. – С. 85-90.
12. Петренко О.В. Актуальні аспекти сучасної моделі людського фактору // Авіа-2015: XII міжнар. наук.-техн. конф., 28-29 квітня 2015 р. – К., 2015. – С. 9.1-9.5.